

Systems Thinking Applied to Slavery

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Abstract - This study utilizes soft system dynamics methodology to analyze modern-day slavery in order to increase understanding and communicate the complexities of slavery. The authors collaborated with Free The Slaves (FTS), a Washington D.C.-based non-governmental organization, in order to gain feedback throughout the modeling process. FTS activists conduct frontline work and have an expertise in understanding how people become susceptible to slavery, victims of slavery, how they are freed, and how they can become slave-proof or highly unlikely to be susceptible to slavery. The authors are currently creating a base macro model of the variables that affect how a community first becomes susceptible to slavery, which will theoretically represent any community in the world. This model will then be tested using assessment data collected by FTS on the North and South Kivu Regions of the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC). This analysis of the DRC may include slavery's roots, geography, growth, magnitude, supply chain of the mining and movement of conflict minerals, the role of law and local organizations, and an overlay of how FTS affects the system. While the ultimate goal for this research is to create proposals for desirable and culturally feasible changes that can reduce the extent of slavery in the North and South Kivu Regions of the DRC, this paper focuses on the first stages of analysis and the base model of the factors that make a community vulnerable to slavery. This paper recommends areas for future research and discussion on how to build further upon the base model.

Index Terms—Slavery, Soft System Dynamics Methodology, Soft Systems Methodology, System Dynamics

LITERATURE REVIEW

The 2013 Global Slavery Index reported that there are 29.8 million people enslaved around the world [1]. Slavery and human trafficking is a multi-faceted international challenge. Human trafficking includes actions within origin, transit, and destination states, yet does not necessitate that victims must travel between nations. The act itself goes beyond the literal term of “human trafficking” and is a form of coercive enslavement used to exploit individuals for labor or sexual services, organ removal or some other type of servitude [2]. As such an illicit issue, researching the statistics on the numbers of victims and profits generated yields a broad range of results. At least 18,000 men, women and children are trafficked into the United States each year according to the United States Justice Department [3], with estimates as

high as 50,000 by the Department of State [4]. While the Global Slavery Index reported nearly thirty million victims of slavery in 2013, a year earlier the United Nations reported that only an estimated 2.45 million people were currently enslaved [5]. Estimates regarding the number of people enslaved annually range from 800,000 to 900,000 all the way to an estimate of 27 million [6]. As for profit, the lower estimates range from seven to ten billion dollars annually [7], however the International Labor Organization’s estimates profits could generate as high as \$32 billion per year [5]. Human trafficking is continually growing and in 2008 was tied with the illegal arms industry as the second largest criminal industry in the world [8]. The numbers alone do not explain the enormity of slavery and human trafficking and its implications on international and national security—ranging from economic and public health consequences to links to terrorism.

This paramount issue pervades every continent, including within the United States. The average age of girls who are enslaved to be sexually exploited in the United States is 13 [3]. If the thousands of people trafficked into the United States is not enough to convince Americans of the United State’s involvement in this international issue, the American consumer’s “slavery footprint” [3] should be—because trafficked persons include those forced into any type of labor and when Americans buy products made by victims of slavery, they only perpetuate the cycle. As a government, the U.S. has created the goal of emancipation for the victims of trafficking both in the U.S. and abroad [9], but current domestic and international institutions are unable to keep up with the pace of this illicit market. According to the 2010 Trafficking in Persons report, there were only 4,166 successful prosecutions around the world that year. The report states, “As long as there are only around 4,000 trafficking convictions worldwide each year, a message is sent that the injustice suffered by victims is not a national or international priority” [10]. FTS prioritizes the liberation of victims and is helping to achieve national goals, such as through their work in the North and South Kivu Regions of the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC).

The DRC is rated by the U.S. State Department as one of the worst nations in the world for human trafficking and slavery because there is no significant effort by the government to end these violations of human rights [11]. According to both the State Department’s annual report and “Congo’s Mining Slaves: Enslavement at South Kivu Mining Sites” conducted by FTS, there are several forms of slavery present within the DRC. Many forms of slavery are directly tied to mining of what has become known as “conflict minerals”—tin, tungsten, tantalum and gold. The

mining of conflict minerals has an extensive supply chain, which when unregulated promotes slavery and therefore makes many private businesses and even private citizens indirect actors because of the products they purchase. There are forms of slavery in nearly every step of the mining process, movement of materials and in the community surrounding the mining site. The types of slavery found in the South Kivu mining sites include forced labor, peonage, sexual slavery, forced prostitution, debt slavery, worst forms of child labor and forced marriage [12]. One in four of those in slavery were under the age of eighteen [12]. The types of severe health problems these children suffer from enslavement in the mines include physical deformities, drug addiction, pulmonary infection, and sexually transmitted diseases [12].

METHODOLOGY

I. System Dynamics (SD)

SD is a fundamentally interdisciplinary approach to learning when dealing with complex systems [13]. SD is grounded in the theory of nonlinear dynamics and feedback control developed in mathematics, physics, and engineering [13]. The SD modeling process consists of five stages. The first stage is problem articulation. In this stage, analysts determine the boundary, theme, key variables, time horizon, and dynamic problem definition [13]. In the second stage, analysts form a dynamic hypothesis by mapping the system utilizing boundary diagrams and subsystem diagrams and generating stock and flow maps. In the third stage, analysts identify model parameters and generate the system model. The fourth stage is the testing stage; sensitivity to initial conditions and parameters is evaluated. The final stage of the SD modeling process is policy design and evaluation. Analysts apply significant effort to “what if analysis” to demonstrate the effects of potential policies [13].

II. Soft Systems Methodology (SSM)

SSM was developed over thirty years at Lancaster University and first published in 1972 by Professor Peter B. Checkland [14]. SSM was created in order to analyze complex primarily social situations that involve the multiple worldviews of different people within the situation. The methodology is action-oriented and its primary purpose is to develop desirable and culturally feasible solutions to improve the situation under study [14]. When Checkland published the first book on SSM in 1981, it had seven stages based upon these above principles. SSM has since been revised into four activities that include all of the previous stages, but allow for a more flexible approach [15]. Despite being the older version of SSM, this study will utilize the seven-stage process. Five of the seven stages are within the “real-world” and utilize people within the situation, while the remaining two stages are within the “systems-thinking” world and do not require the involvement of the people within the problematic situation [15]. The following are the seven stages in detail:

Stage 1 The Problem Situation Unstructured: After indentifying a problematic situation in which there exists a desire for change, analysts first attempt to describe the situation in which the problem takes place (versus the problem itself) [15]. During this stage, analysts must keep their findings broad and attempt to discover trends that exist within the environment and are likely to affect the problematic situation. Trends may include those found in the economy, politics, society, technology, law, culture, ethics, ideology, customs, and ethics [15].

Stage 2 The Problem Situation Expressed: During this stage, the elements recorded in the first stage become linked and analysts begin to indentify stakeholders and to model the situation graphically. Throughout this process, analysts must be cognizant of their own perceptions and ensure they are not biased when they begin modeling. In order to articulate the problematic situation all of the relationships are demonstrated through systems models such as rich pictures [15]. A rich picture is created using pictures and arrows to show the relationships between key variables and it is used to invite discussion amongst analysts, clients, and stakeholders, especially when the latter two groups are not systems engineers. Checkland writes that the goal of a rich picture is to “...capture, informally, the main entities, structures and viewpoints in the situation, the processes going on, the current recognized issues and any potential ones” [14].

Stage 3 Root Definitions of Relevant Systems: This stage begins with a discussion on what systems identified in stages 1 and 2 are the most relevant to the problematic situation and after identifying these areas the practitioners can begin to form definitions to describe them [15]. Each definition will apply to what Checkland calls a “purposeful activity” or a human situation in which people are acting purposefully [14]. Each definition is from a specific world view or *Weltanschauung* and is known as a “root definition” [15]. A root definition can be written like a hypothesis and can describe desired behavior, though in some cases it may be more beneficial or more relevant to describe the system as a problem [15]. To aid in developing root definitions Checkland also created the mnemonic CATWOE, which includes all of the components necessary: **Customers:** people affected by the activity—its beneficiaries or victims. **Actors:** the people required to complete the activity. **Transformation:** the process the activity completes. This process is monitored for efficacy, efficiency, and effectiveness. **Weltanschauung:** worldview or point-of-view from which the definition is being described. **Owners:** the person or persons who are viewed as owning the activity. **Environment:** the conditions and constraints under which the activity takes place [14].

Stage 4 Making and Testing Conceptual Models: After developing root definitions, a conceptual model is created for each definition that consists of an ordered list of activities needed to accomplish what the root definition specifies. The model is notional and does not describe the real world but is solely derived from the root definition;

therefore, any changes to the definition must be reflected in its conceptual model and vice versa. The only way to validate a conceptual model is to test its logic through a comparison with formal system models, which are general models of any kind of human activity system [15].

Stage 5 Comparing Conceptual Models with Reality:

During this stage, the conceptual models are compared to their corresponding real-world systems that were identified in the problem situation. The goal of this stage is to begin a debate on what changes proposed in the conceptual models should be introduced into the real world. There are four techniques practitioners can use for comparison: ordered questioning, examination of the past, identify major differences and a real-world model overlay. In ordered questioning, the conceptual models are used to incite debate and questioning regarding the actual situation amongst people involved; the answers to these questions then further illustrate the problems within the situation. In examining the past, conceptual models are applied to a series of past events and a comparison is drawn between what actually happened and what would be believed to happen had the conceptual models been in place. The comparison can also be applied generally and practitioners can identify the major differences between the conceptual models and reality. Lastly, a second model of the real world can be created in the same form as the conceptual model; the only changes between the two models are the differences between the notional world and reality. Once the model is complete, it is overlaid with the conceptual model and the differences are even more apparent. During this stage, any one or combinations of the comparison methods can be used. The comparison stage may illuminate changes that need to be made to past stages in SSM as well as suggest changes that can be made to the problem situation [15].

Stage 6 Culturally Feasible and Desirable Changes:

From the debate caused by the comparison stage, practitioners can develop a list of potential changes to be made to the problem situation. The changes can be classified as structure, procedure, or attitude changes. While the first two changes can be made relatively easily, the last type of change is the most difficult to implement. To determine potential changes, the discussion should include people who are interested in affecting the problem situation and are likely the ones who will help implement the change. Once changes are proposed analysts work with the concerned actors to determine if a change is both desirable (based on information from the conceptual models and root definitions) and feasible (based on the situation, the people involved and the various worldviews) [15].

Stage 7 Action to Improve the Problem Situation:

This stage involves working closely with concerned actors in order to determine how the desirable and culture changes can be implemented.

Once all seven stages are complete, the analysts have successfully analyzed a problem situation, created culturally and desirable changes and begun implementing them. Throughout the process, the practitioners should reflect on

the progress they are making and on the methodology and case as a whole once they have finished [14].

III. Soft System Dynamics Methodology (SSDM)

SSDM was created by Professor Ricardo Rodriguez-Ulloa during his research from 1992 to 1999. Rodriguez-Ulloa built upon Checkland's seven-stage methodology and created his own theory combining SSM with SD. SSDM is the primary methodology used for this project. The methodology consists of ten stages and is conducted within three different worlds: the real world, the problem-situation-oriented system thinking world, and the solving-situation-oriented system thinking world [16].

Real World: Stage 1 (The Problem Situation Unstructured) Stage 2 (The Problem Situation Expressed): These stages are the same as stages 1 and 2 of SSM involving the analysis of the environment and its trends and the creation of a rich picture.

Problem-Situation Systems Thinking World: Stage 3 (Problem-Oriented Rich Definitions): This stage is also borrowed from SSM but instead of creating definitions that are aimed at describing solutions or changes, the root definitions with SSDM express what is occurring in the real world through describing the problematic transformation processes. **Stage 4: Building System Dynamics Models of the "Problem Situation":** During this stage, analysts apply SD to construct a context diagram that models the problematic situation according to a specified world view. Next, a causal loop is designed for each root definition created in stage 3. The causal loops are analyzed through multiple iterations and a sensitivity analysis in order to better understand the relationship between variables within each root definition that again correspond to a particular world view. The most important part of this stage is gaining an increased understanding of the overall problematic situation through analyzing all of the root definitions, world views, causal loops, and context diagrams.

Real World: Stage 5: Compare Stage 4 Against 2: Compare the rich picture with the causal loop and context diagrams in order to validate the terminology of the systems dynamics models and if they accurately describe the real world.

Solving-Situation Systems Thinking World: Stage 6: Determine Culturally Feasible and Systematically Desirable Changes: After conducting stage 5, analysts determine which variables or links within the models can be changed to affect positively the problematic situation. **Stage 7: Building System Dynamics Models of the "Solving Situation":** During this stage, it is determined whether the changes proposed in stage 6 are desirable and culturally feasible through the creation and iteration of a context diagram modeling the proposed change. Another sensitivity analysis is conducted to understand further the consequences of varying different variables. **Stage 8: Solving Situation-Oriented Root Definitions:** During this stage, analysts create root definitions that describe the transformation the desirable and feasible changes hope to

make. This includes a CATWOE analysis from SSM. These definitions are then compared to the real world problematic situation to determine whether the changes could be implemented.

Real World: Stage 9: Implementation of Feasible and Desirable Changes in the Real World. Stage 10: Learning Points: Analysts compile any of the key learning takeaways they had during the process especially during the sensitivity analysis of stage 4, the sensitivity analysis of stage 7 and how the changes were implemented into the real world [16].

ANALYSIS

In conjunction with FTS, the authors have completed the initial analysis for stages 1 and 2 of SSDM as well as created a base system dynamics model for stage 4. This initial research does not include root definitions (stage 3) for the model, because the number of root definitions describing slavery in general is nearly infinite. Rather in future research when the analysis is narrowed to the DRC, the authors will begin to develop root definitions and corresponding casual loops.

FIGURE 1
RICH PICTURE FOR GENERAL MODEL

Stage 1 (The Problem Situation Unstructured): This stage referring to slavery in general is discussed in the literature review. **Stage 2 (The Problem Situation Expressed):** Figure 1 is the initial rich picture that was created primarily based on meetings with FTS along with research on slavery to include the Department of State’s Annual Trafficking in Persons report, The 2013 Global Slavery Index, reports conducted by FTS, books by Kevin Bales, and documents from the United Nations amongst others. Both the rich picture and following definitions were adjusted after receiving feedback from FTS.

Community: a group of people with some kind of unifying factor such as location, religion, culture, history, ethnicity or some combination of these or other unifying factors.

External Factors: *Involvement of international organizations and other countries:* Includes both beneficial and harmful organizations and country involvement. Examples of positive organizations are NGOs like FTS and the United Nations while harmful examples are terrorist groups and criminal networks. *Media coverage of slavery:* Media coverage of slavery within that region or state and how accessible that media is to members of the community, others within the region, state and universally.

Supply: *Birth Rate:* The number of live births in the country per year (utilize regional data if possible). *Death Rate:* The number of deaths in the country per year (utilize regional data if possible).

Geography: *Neighboring countries politics:* Includes the movement and existence of refugees, presence of armed conflict, political instability, corruption and any other factors that may negatively influence the stability of the community. *Permeability of borders:* how likely the neighboring countries’ politics are to affect the community. Also includes the existence of trafficking and slavery regulations effectively executed at the border.

State: *Corruption:* Any form of corruption that may affect the execution of anti-slavery practices, increase the instability of a government, or make government, law or law enforcement officials unreliable. *Government stability:* Conflict and war torn countries. With a decrease in corruption and conflict, this will begin to rise significantly. *Gross Domestic Product (GDP):* a country’s GDP is assessed in part to determine if the country or specific region has available funding for organizations that can produce job opportunities and regulate human rights violations. (For example, the D.R.C’s GDP would rise significantly if the country gains control over its natural resources and does not allow Rwanda or Uganda to exploit them further.) *Conflict:* Armed conflict exists within the country. *Pro-human rights organizations (local):* Pro-human rights organizations exist and are active at the local level. *Rule of law:* Laws regulating commerce and human rights exist, are enforced by law enforcement, and upheld by the judiciary system. *Government Accountability:* what measurements exist to hold the government and its officials accountable (to include judges and police officers among others) and how effective these measurements are. *Service provision:* how basic services such as welfare, medical care, hospital and legal services are supposed to be provided to community members and how they are actually provided if at all (for example this may be through a well-functioning government or from an NGO).

Formal Education: *Level of available education:* specifies the educational opportunities available and the highest level of education offered to members of the community. *Access to education:* who within the community has access to educational opportunities and to what level; restrictions may include a person’s wealth, gender, or class. Access is determined by local government and cultural norms. *Quality of education:* Amount of knowledge accessible to students (based on the level of

restriction a government, cultural ideology or some other external organization places on education). Also includes the level of student achievement as assessed by an international large-scale assessment if possible.

Access to Information: *Awareness of slavery:* Level of local awareness of slavery due to media, anti-slavery NGOs, and any other groups educating the population. *Awareness of rights:* Level of awareness community members have in regards to the rights guaranteed by their local government and state governments (if there are any protections). Also includes awareness of basic human rights as established by the United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

Culture: *Labor culture:* the acceptance of unpaid labor through tradition or cultural means (such as salongo in Congo) and the regulations placed upon workers and working conditions (such as age limits, working hours etc.). *Value placed on life:* a cultural assessment of whom a community believes has a right to live. For example, are all people's lives within the community valued and protected (such as by law enforcement agencies) or is there discrimination against genders, castes, religion, refugees, non-citizens or other factors. Within the rich picture, it is assumed that there is some bias for who has value placed upon their lives within the community. *Strength of familial bonds:* a measure of the cultural acceptance towards slavery based on the strength of family ties, cultural responsibilities of each member of the family or any other factor related to the family (family unit as defined by the community). *History of slavery:* existence of slavery within the community at any other point in time. *Traditions:* existence of social constructs practiced throughout a prolonged period that involves the enslavement of certain community members such as forced marriage and child servitude.

Demand: *Availability of high demand resources:* the presence of areas within the region that can be exploited by slave labor (i.e. mines, forests, farm land). *Demand for slavery:* demand for all types of slavery within the region to include sexual slavery, forced labor, debt bondage, peonage, forced marriage, child labor, victims for organ removal, forced prostitution, trafficked slaves, and any other type of slavery. *Demand for goods made by slave labor:* demand by private consumers and business within the region, the state and internationally.

Business: *Market price:* the market price for anything a slave may be exploited for (i.e. labor, prostitution, and organs). *Profitability of slavery:* the presence of any dissuading factors against using slavery, without any of these factors slavery will be more profitable than legal means. (Does the punishment to traffickers/slave owners outweigh the benefits of free labor?) *Regulations on trade and labor:* presence of laws in place to prevent human trafficking and all forms of slavery at a regional, national, and/or international level. *Environmental destruction:* The amount of natural resource consumption, destruction, and pollution within a region as connected with slave labor. *Supply chain transparency:* how transparent the movement of goods involving slave labor by the community members

is. This includes the transparency from the goods' source, while in transit and at the destination.

Family Resources and Livelihood: *Access to financial services:* access to non-corrupt banks for loans and proper education on financial services (both of which help prevent debt labor). *Ability to find a job:* rate of unemployment and available legal job opportunities; determines whether community members are likely to seek job opportunities that may be ploys to enslave them. *Standard of Living:* the standard of living for community members, this relates to job opportunities and expectations for living conditions.

Technology: The prevalence and use of technology by anti-slavery actors as well as traffickers and slave owners—can be manipulated to benefit either party.

Stage 4: Building System Dynamics Models of the “Problem Situation”: Figure II represents a base model of a community under the threat of human trafficking and slavery. The model was created using Vensim software.

FIGURE II
SYSTEM DYNAMICS BASE MODEL

The model shows that the total population of the community can be divided into three categories: population susceptible to human trafficking, population enslaved or trafficked, and slave proof. The population susceptible to human trafficking is the section of the population that is under a constant threat of being enslaved. The population enters this stock by being born to parents who either are enslaved or are in the susceptible population already. It is assumed that an individual cannot be born into slavery, so if both parents are enslaved they are susceptible until they hit an age in which they can become victims of slavery. Until that point, they are considered susceptible to human trafficking. People within this community can also enter this population after being freed from slavery when they are not provided with the knowledge and resources to become part of the slave proof population. The population enslaved or trafficked, is the part of the population that is currently enslaved or being trafficked. Finally, the slave proof population is the portion of the population that cannot be enslaved and is no longer susceptible to enslavement. Members of the community become part of this population

when they find the means to protect themselves from enslavement or trafficking. The authors determined that although it is possible for a person to move from slave proof to susceptible or enslaved, the low probability makes it irrelevant to the model. Factors that may lead to a person belonging within the slave proof population include an awareness of slavery, increased education, a higher standard of living, and other factors. It was also assumed that children born to slave proof parents are part of the slave proof population.

Members of the community move between the three populations but eventually exit the model when they die. All three stocks have associated death rates. It was assumed that the difference between the death rate for population susceptible to human trafficking and slave proof is so miniscule that it has no effect on the model. Therefore, they both share a standard death rate. The death rate of the population enslaved will be much higher than the other two death rates based on the nature of the difference in lifestyles. The authors assumed that the death rate for victims within the enslaved or trafficked population is twice the standard death rate.

CONCLUSION

Soft system dynamics methodology was chosen in this case study because of its appeal as a process that uses both hard and soft systems concepts. While Checkland's SSM was designed to model human situations in which there is a demand for change, the application of system dynamics allows practitioners to analytically model how those changes may affect the problematic situation, adding quantitative credibility to a largely conceptual methodology.

When analyzing slavery it soon becomes apparent how complex of a problematic situation it is. After conducting research and working with FTS to develop a rich picture eleven categories were identified as consisting of major variables that contribute to what makes a community vulnerable to slavery. Within this study a base system dynamics model was developed that focuses solely on the central variable of "community." In future research, root definitions would next be created (SSDM stage 3) for every major variable or set of variables within the rich picture and corresponding casual loops developed to then add to this study's base model. The three primary rates that the casual loops would influence within the base model would be the rate at which a person moves into a susceptible population, a slavery proof population, or an enslaved population. By analyzing the variables that affect such rates practitioners would begin to be able to understand questions such as how people become enslaved, how slavery can be prevented, how victims can be rescued and why slavery exists. The goal of this research is to create a starting point for future work that will model slavery in general and slavery in specific cases such as in the North and South Kivu regions of the DRC. From these advanced models, SSDM can be followed in order to develop feasible and culturally appropriate proposals.

While this research does not yet complete the entire SSDM process, it does demonstrate how complex slavery is. This study only conducts stages 1, 2 and the beginning of 4, yet even these stages can be re-analyzed and expanded. This report also serves to show the value systems thinking can play in analyzing slavery's complexity and eventually proposing policies to address this global issue. Therefore, the authors have realized the benefit of applying systems thinking to slavery and recommend that future research be conducted to increase understanding of how slavery develops, how it can be prevented, and how its victims can be freed.

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